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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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THE IMPACT OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION AND TECHNOLOGY ON EFFECTIVE EDUCATIONAL PLANNING IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

In the twenty-first century, the impact of information communication technology and effective educational planning were investigated. The study used a descriptive survey research design. 1,250 employees of the Ministry of Education in Osun state, Nigeria made up the research area's population. For the study, a sample of 400 respondents was chosen using multi stage sampling technique. The Information Communication Technology and Effective Educational Planning Questionnaire (ICTAEEPQ) was the instrument utilized in this study. To determine the instrument's consistency, the validity of its face and content were determined. Using the test-retest reliability approach, the instrument was administered twice within two weeks, the data generated was analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation and a reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained which is high enough to make the instrument reliable. The acquired data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings indicated that there was no available ICT gadget in educational planning in the Ministry of Education in Osun state, Nigeria. There was a significant impact of ICT on effective educational planning in Osun state and there was no significant impact of ICT application in educational planning in the 21st century in Osun state, Nigeria. Conclusion and recommendations were made to include Training and retraining of educational planning need to be introduced and strengthened especially in the area of ICT usage and application in the planning of education in Osun state.

Keywords: Information Communication Technology, Education, Planning, Educational Planning and computer literacy.

INTRODUCTION

Education, banking, agriculture and security have all benefited in one way or the other as regards information communication and technology "ICT". For example, in the banking sector a few decades prior, clients had to wait longer than necessary in line to make payments to or take money from their accounts. But now, things are not the same. It is impossible to overstate the significant contribution that ICT has made to the unexpectedly fast pace at which information is spreading. In today's world, the amount of information about ICT is rapidly growing. Without the aid of ICT devices, very few tasks can be completed or managed effectively. Educational planners have indeed benefited greatly from this new technology. Having proficient computer skills is now a need for any endeavour undertaken by a human (Rahimullah, 2015). A collection of automated procedures that make up the foundation of

information technology (IT) nowadays includes learning skills and some other administrative tasks. (Mukherjee, et.al, 2014).

Compared to earlier times, there is a growing desire for computer literacy these days. Experience has demonstrated how pervasive a superficial understanding of computer and ICT literacy has become in all areas of life (Hoar, 2014). Computers and other ICT devices are replacing human labour in every facet of human endeavours, workers have also come to understand that these devices pose a threat to their jobs. The only way out is to understand what abilities must be acquired to maintain one source of income. Professionals are becoming concerned about teaching and mastering computer literacy due to the increasing demand and desire for this expertise. These days, it's evident that barely any establishment, organization or even educational institution is visible without a computer.

Education has been perceived as any act or experience that has a formative impact on a person's mind, character, or physical ability. It includes the process of imparting knowledge to a novice to assist them in developing certain attitudes and skills that are valued and desired in society (Bragg, et. al 2017). The goal of educational planning is to investigate, create, carry out, and promote reforms, policies, and programs in educational establishments. To enhance or progress education, educational planners may operate locally, nationally, or worldwide.

In the realm of education, planning is crucial. It is referred to as "Educational Planning," and it is a major necessity which must be given specific consideration to the importance of planning in education (Usman, 2016). Similar to planning in any other discipline, educational planning must investigate the most effective ways to maximize the use of resources available to achieve the goals and objectives of education, both social and individual (Yıkıcı and Altınay, 2018). Inadequate ICT infrastructure and accessibility also contribute to the negative sentiments that businesses and employees have about technology. In many ministries, there isn't even one computer and the ones that are frequently being used improperly. To aid them with their everyday tasks, many educational planners receive training using antiquated materials and have little to no access to information communication and technology. This comes as a surprise given the federal government's position on ICT use in national organizations, ministries, and schools. ICT is now a necessary component of the modern world and has been incorporated into the educational system in Nigeria. Experience has shown that most educational planners lack the required skills of computers and other ICT gadgets which has posed some difficulties in making effective planning. We are in a global world where knowledge of yesterday has become outdated due to innovation and technology. Paperwork in the planning stages may no longer be effective as the world moves faster than expected.

Planning is forward-thinking and might be internal, external, or instantaneous. The three main categories of planning are short, middle and long-term. In education, planning is extremely important and critical. It is widely accepted that defining one's goals in advance is the first step toward achieving them. The saying goes, "If you can't plan, you should be planning to fail." All human endeavours are included in planning. The purpose of educational planning is to establish the philosophy, policies, programs, and tactics for accomplishing educational goals as well as to predetermine those goals. For planning to be effective and efficient, educational planners must be certified in ICT and other ICT gadgets.

It has been observed globally, that ICT and computer compliance are in high demand and educational planners need to be acquainted with the required skills to make them function properly and effectively. It appears that educational planners do not key into this new trend. Several organizations, government agencies and educational planners still harbour reservations about embracing ICT literacy and usage in their organizations. Some of them employ secretaries to carry out their secretarial duties and are very reluctant to acquire the necessary training required for better task performance. The problem of the study put in question form is what are the available ICT devices, ICT application in educational planning and their impact on effective educational planning in Osun state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study investigated the impact of information communication and technology on effective educational planning in the 21st century in Osun state, Nigeria. The Specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Investigate the availability of ICT gadgets in educational planning in Osun state.
2. Examine the Impact of ICT on effective educational planning in Osun State
3. Investigate ICT in educational planning in the 21st century

Research Question

1. What is the level of availability of ICT gadgets in educational planning in Osun state, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between ICT and effective educational planning in Osun state.
2. There is no significant relationship between applications of ICT gadgets and effective educational planning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A framework of Information Communication and Technology (ICT)

Information communication and technologies (ICT) play a significant role in all aspects of modern society. As ICT affect everyday lives, it also impacts macroeconomic growth, which in turn further affects society by enabling infrastructure and standard of living improvements (Nordin, 2021). Information communications and technology (ICT) Skills Framework for the Information Age is one of many models for describing and managing competencies for ICT professionals in the 21st century (Brown, 2020).

According to Li and Chan (2019) argued that concept of information technology (IT) is the harnessing electronic of technology for the information processing needs of business organizations using computer and telecommunications-based equipment for storage, processing and dissemination of information It is an umbrella term associated with terms such as video conferencing and distance learning. Achimug and Abraham, (2019) viewed information communication and technologies (ICT) are electronic technologies used for information storage and retrieval. The rate through which ICTs have evolved since the mid-20th century, the convergence and pervasiveness of ICTs, give them a strong role in development and globalization ICTs have a significant impact on all areas of human activity. It seems the field of education has been affected by ICTs, which have undoubtedly affected teaching, learning and research. Engaging students, to help relate school experience to work practices, create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, as well as strengthen teaching

and helping schools to change. The Economic Commission for Africa has indicated that the ability to access and use information is no longer a luxury, but a necessity for development. Unfortunately, many developing countries, especially in Africa, are still low in ICT application and usage. Ponomareva, (2021). predicted, the knowledge of computers has joined (or even surpassed) the knowledge of mathematics as a critical filter for employment opportunities in many opportunities most individuals may wish to pursue as careers. Makori, (2017), argued that computer revolution will continue to have a more ubiquitous impact on the lives of individuals through economic, cultural and social institutions that impact society. The importance of information communication and technology (ICT) facilities in effective educational planning in the Ministry of Education, Osun state, Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized. Hamilton-Ekeke and Mbachu (2015). posited that information communication and technology (ICT) have become key tools and had a revolutionary impact on how we see the world and how we live. Today, the place of ICT in effective educational planning and the world in general cannot be undermined. He contended that modern-day business is conducted and facilitated using telephones, fax machines and computer communication networks through the Internet. The phenomenon has given birth to contemporary e-commerce, e-government, e-Learning, e-medicine and e-banking among others. There's a need to brace up to the new challenges through the development and use of ICT in government parastatals. Already, Nigeria is almost two decades behind in embracing the use of computers and other ICT devices in government parastatals. Kingsley, A. (2017), opined that ICT fosters the dissemination of information and knowledge by separating content from its physical location. This flow of information is largely impervious to geographic boundaries allowing remote communities to become integrated into global networks and making information, knowledge and culture accessible, in theory, to anyone. According to Niaz (2020), observed the effective utilization of ICT in human resource management depends on the availability of these facilities and human resource competence in using them.

Information communication and technology (ICT) may be used in different ways in the management of schools (Abdul-Salaam, A. O. (2017). The author notes further that various ICT facilities used in effective educational planning include radio, television, computers, overhead projectors, optical fibres, fax machines, CD-ROM, internet, electronic notice board, slides, digital multimedia, and videos / vcg machines mention a few.

Akpan-Obong, (2023). reveal in his respective studies that, limited /poor information infrastructure inhibits the use of ICT by human resource management, ICT development and application are not well established in the civil service commission. Moreover, Ayeni (2013) investigated on effective utilization and maintenance of ICT facilities for quality teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. The author found that ICT facilities are not available for teaching and learning in Ondo State public secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive research of the survey type with 1,250 educational planners in the ministries and state universal basic education board in Osun state as the population while 400 respondents were selected as the samples for the study. "Information Communication Technology and Effective Educational Planning Questionnaire" (ICTAEEPQ) was the instrument utilized in this study. Four-point Likert scales of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree, where SA, A, D and SD stand for 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. To determine the instrument's consistency, the validity of its face and content were determined. Using the test-retest reliability approach, the instrument was administered twice within two weeks, the data generated was analysed using the Pearson Product Moment

Correlation and a reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained which was high enough to make the instrument reliable. The acquired data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

FINDINGS

Q₁: What is the level of availability of ICT gadgets in effective educational planning in the Ministry of Education, Osun state?

Table.1. indicate the research question on the availability of ICT gadgets in effective educational planning

ICT gadgets	Frequency	Percentages
Yes	115	28.75%
No	285	71.25%
Total	400	100%

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentages of the respondents based on the availability of ICT gadgets in effective educational planning in Osun State. The results indicated that 115 respondents amounting to 28.75% agreed with the statements and 285 respondents amounting to 71.25% disagreed with the statements.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between ICT and effective educational planning in Osun state.

Table 2. Impact of ICT on effective educational planning in Osun state

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	t-crit	p-value
ICT	400	29.24	13.43	.229	0.195	0.000
Edu plan	400	83.33	9.86			

From Table.2: The result obtained showed that the value of t-calculated = .229, $p = .000$. This indicates a significant impact of ICT on effective educational planning in Osun state, Nigeria because the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, H_1 states that there is no significant impact of ICT on effective educational planning in Osun state was rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between applications of ICT gadgets and effective educational planning.

Table 3. Application of ICT gadgets on effective educational planning

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-cal	t-crit
ICT Application	400	43.04	9.32	.137	0.195
Effective Educational Planning	400	85.12	9.86		

The above result showed the application of ICT gadgets in effective educational planning in the 21st-century Osun state. The result indicated that the value of t-calculated (0.137) was less than r-critical (0.195). This indicates the significant impact of ICT application in educational planning in the 21st century Osun State. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

DISCUSSION

The study investigated the Impact of information communications and technology on effective educational planning in the 21st century Osun state, Nigeria. Findings revealed that 115 respondents amounting to 28.75% agreed with the statements and 285 respondents amounting to 71.25% disagreed with the statements on the availability of ICT gadgets in educational planning in Osun state, this also confirmed that there is no availability of ICT gadgets in effective educational planning in Osun state. Akpan-Obong, (2023). reveal in his respective studies that, limited /poor information infrastructure inhibits the use of ICT by human resource management, ICT development and application are not well established in the civil service commission. Moreso, Ayeni (2013) investigated on effective utilization and maintenance of ICT facilities for quality teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. The author found that ICT facilities are not available for teaching and learning in Ondo State public secondary schools.

Hypothesis one states that there was no significant impact of ICT on effective educational planning in Osun state. From the analysis, the result obtained showed that the value of r-calculated = .229, $p = .000$. This indicates a significant impact of ICT on effective educational planning in the Ministry of Education Osun state, Nigeria. According to Achimugu and Abraham, (2019), information communication and technologies (ICT) are electronic technologies used for information storage and retrieval. The rapid rate at which ICTs have evolved since the mid-20th century, the convergence and pervasiveness of ICTs, give them a strong role in development and globalization ICTs have a significant impact on all areas of human activity.

Hypothesis two states that, from the analysis of the application of ICT application in effective educational planning in the 21st century. The result indicated that the value of t-calculated (0.137) was less than r-critical (0.195). This indicates the significant impact of ICT application in educational planning in the 21st century Osun State. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicates the significant impact of ICT application in effective educational planning. Information communication and technology (ICT) may be used in different ways in the management of schools (Abdul-Salaam, 2017). The author notes further that various ICT facilities used in effective educational planning include radio, television, computers, overhead projectors, optical fibres, fax machines, CD-ROM, internet, electronic notice board, slides, digital multimedia, and videos / vcg machines mention a few.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the impact of information communication and technology on effective educational planning in the 21st century. It can also be concluded that effective educational planning can easily be attainable when educational planners are acquainted with the needed I. T. skills to better their decision making and efficient implementation of policies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made,

- There is a need for the provision of basic and applied ICT equipment and gadgets to all the educational planning departments and units in Osun state.
- Training and retraining in educational planning need to be introduced and strengthened especially in the area of ICT usage and application in the planning of education in Osun state.

- Educational planning in the Osun state should partner with ICT units for training on the modern techniques of planning using ICT gadgets and equipment

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